

Chemosensors based on diazole derivatives

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Abstract : The heterocyclic diazole compounds and their derivatives not only exhibit a wide range of pharmacological activity but also can act as bioagent and revolve around its ability to bond to various guests as host. Hence it is useful in designing chemosensors. This review summarizes the most recent and relevant advances in this area.

Keywords : Diazole, bioagent, chemosensors.

Introduction

Azoles are five-membered heterocyclic compounds having a nitrogen atom and at least one other non-carbon atom (i.e. nitrogen, sulfur or oxygen) as part of the ring, diazoles refer to a special class of azoles as these are also five-membered aromatic heterocyclic compounds consisting of three carbon atoms and two nitrogen heteroatoms. Their names have been derived from the Hantzsch-Widman nomenclature (also called the extended Hantzsch-Widman system), where the numbering of the ring atoms in azoles starts with the heteroatom that is not part of a double bond, and then proceeds towards the other heteroatom. These compounds having two double bonds are aromatic in nature due to the participation of only one lone pair of electrons of each heteroatom in the ring as a part of the aromatic bonding in an azole. The two double bonds of the parent compound could be successively reduced to produce reduced analog with fewer like azolines and azolidines and upon reduction the names of azoles maintain the prefix e.g. pyrazoline, pyrazolidine.

Such heterocyclic units have many uses. They exhibit a wide range of pharmacological activity, ubiquitous in nature and play a critical role in many structures within the human body, notably histamine and hystidine which contain imidazole unit. A special interest of researchers towards benzimidazole derivatives was stimulated by the fact that 5,6-dimethyl-1-

(α -dribofuranosyl)benzimidazole is an basic part of the structure of vitamine B12¹, and benzimidazole is a structural unit of naturally occurring nucleotide, due to which it can easily interact with the biopolymers of living system, which is responsible for its numerous biological aspects. Diazoles like benzimidazole and pyrazole ring become an important pharmacophore in modern drug discovery²⁻⁴. Moreover dazoles can be used as bioagent and its ability to bond to various guests as ligand make it useful in designing chemosensors for various ions. This review covers recent important development of diazole (here benzimidazole and pyrazole) as receptors for the recognition of various anions, cations and neutral molecules.

Imidazole/benzimidazole based compounds as chemosensor

Benzimidazole ring behaves as an excellent hydrogen bond donor moiety in synthetic anion receptor systems, and the acidity of the NH proton of the imidazole can be tuned by changing the electronic properties of the imidazole substituents. On the other hand, the presence of a donor pyridine-like nitrogen atom within the ring, capable of selectively binding cationic species also converts the imidazole derivatives into excellent metal ion sensors. Due to the emissive properties of the aromatic ring, benzimidazole has also been commonly used in molecular recognition of all cations, anions and neutral molecules. As a result, this

moiety has been used not only as a binding unit for cations and anions, as the imidazole derivatives do, but also as a fluorogenic antenna. Another fact with the imidazole ring is the two NH protons of different acidity caused by the electronic effect of the benzene ring. Here we cover important development of benzimidazole derivative receptors for the recognition of various anions, cations and neutral molecules. We have grouped the receptors to their ion sensing which include cations, anions, cations-anions both and neutral molecules which behaving as sensors for different ions.

Chemosensors for cations :

In the field of molecular recognition of cations García and co-workers had mentioned the macrocyclic ligand, **1** (Table 1). The N and S atoms present in this system act as recognition sites while the two benzimidazole units act as fluorescent antenna for the detection of transition metal cations in water⁵. A bathochromic shift in the UV-Vis bands upon addition of the corresponding cations is due to the metal coordination. Titration experiments carried out by using this technique were used to calculate the association constant of the different complexes, showing a higher affinity towards Cr^{3+} , followed by the Fe^{2+} cation, while other metal cations as Hg^{2+} or Cd^{2+} have much smaller association constants. The selectivity found in this receptor has been attributed to the relative Lewis acidity of the cations that dominates the coordination capabilities of the receptor. The small selectivity in the process indicates that fluorescence quenching has a diffusive behaviour.

Fahrni's group developed a Zn^{2+} -selective ratiometric biologically suitable probe (**2**) showed the cation-induced inhibition of excited-state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT) with a series of 2-(2'-benzenesulfonamidophenyl)benzimidazole derivatives in emission study⁶. In the absence of Zn^{2+} at neutral pH, the fluorophores undergo ESIPT to yield a highly Stokes' shifted emission from the proton-transfer tautomer. Coordination of Zn^{2+} inhibits the ESIPT process and yields a significant hypsochromic shift of the fluorescence emission maximum. Due to the modular architecture of the fluorophore, the Zn^{2+} binding affinity can be readily tuned by implementing simple

structural modifications. The synthesized probes are suitable to gauge free Zn^{2+} concentrations in the micromolar to picomolar range under physiological conditions.

Guo and co-workers devised a fluorescent 2-(2'-pyridinyl)benzimidazole based Zn^{2+} sensor (**3**)⁷. The sensor demonstrates a Zn^{2+} -specific emission shift and enhancement with a 1 : 1 binding ratio. Due to the Zn^{2+} -induced coplanation via reversion/rotation, the sensor behaves as a ratiometric sensor. The intracellular Zn^{2+} imaging ability of the sensor has been tested in HeLa cells using a confocal microscope.

Rao and co-workers has reported the benzimidazole-substituted calix[4]arene (**4**) for the selective recognition of Hg^{2+} versus a large number of divalent cations (Table 1)⁸ in MeOH, anhydrous CH_3CN and also in different aqueous mixtures of this organic solvent. In 50% aqueous solution, a 10-fold quenching in the fluorescence was observed only in the case of Hg^{2+} , whereas all other divalent metal cations tested exhibited almost no quenching in fluorescent intensity. However, when the amount of water decreases, the selectivity for this cation also decreases, due to the effect of a less competitive media. Binding of Hg^{2+} has been attributed, by ¹H NMR experiments, to the nitrogen atoms in the benzimidazole ring and the oxygen atoms of the amide bridge, as the theoretical calculations also predicted. The Hg^{2+} -complex formed has been isolated, characterized and studied on surface by TEM, SEM and AFM microscopies.

Minkin and co-workers synthesized a number of 1-(9-anthrylmethyl)-2-aryl-1*H*-benzimidazoles (**5**)⁹. Study on their luminescent properties and complexing ability showed that the sensitivity of these systems to H^+ and Hg^{2+} ions is related to fluorescence quenching by the action of these cations and effectively selective towards H^+ and Hg^{2+} ions.

Jang's group synthesized a benzimidazole-based fluorescent receptor (**6**) bearing imine linkages with two sets of sp^2 nitrogens, and investigated its binding properties toward various metal ions¹⁰. The receptor exhibited a shift in emission band upon binding with Fe^{3+} ions, and no such significant response was noticed in other metal ions. The receptor shows a prop-

erty of selective ratiometric fluorescent probe of Fe^{3+} ions without interferences of the background metal ions.

Singh and co-workers have synthesized a novel fluorescent receptor (**7**) based upon a benzimidazole moiety in a dipodal framework¹¹. The receptor exhibited a dual fluorescence emission which is quenched upon addition of Cu^{2+} or Fe^{3+} . Interestingly, the receptor

offers a ratiometric property and an 'OR' logic gate property to Cu^{2+} and Fe^{3+} .

A different approach has been followed by Tang and Nandhakumar who designed a Rhodamine B colorimetric chemosensor (**8**) based on the chemical changes induced by Cu^{II} anion (Table 1)¹². UV-Vis experiments demonstrated that upon addition of Cu^{II} the

Table 1. Benzimidazole based chemosensors recognizing cations

Table-1 (contd.)

(10)

(11)

(12)

(13)

(14)

(15)

(16)

(17)

a : R=H
b : R=CH₃

(18)

(19)

(20)

(21)

(22)

(23)

(24)

Table-1 (contd.)

change of colour in the solution from colourless to pink with appearance of a low energy band. This colour change has been attributed to a ring-opening process of the spirolactam form of chemosensor (**8**). Addition of other metal cations does not produce such changes in the absorption spectrum and does not disturb the effect of Cu^{II} in competitiveness experiments. The reversibility of the process has confirmed by the addition of EDTA to the medium that cause the disappearance of colour, returning the solution to the initial colourless appearance.

A rhodamine-benzimidazole conjugate (**9**) was designed and synthesized by Li and co-workers which detect selectivity Fe^{3+} in a 1 : 1 stoichiometry over other metal ions in acetonitrile¹³. A thousand time fluorescence intensity enhancement was observed at the maximum emission wavelength of 582 nm upon the addition of 10 equiv. of Fe^{3+} the detection limit was $1.5 \times 10^{-8} \text{ M}$.

Wang and co-workers synthesized a dehydroabietyl molecule (**10**) with a benzimidazole unit for the molecular recognition of metal cations¹⁴. Receptor (**10**) decreases its fluorescent emission at $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 540 \text{ nm}$ upon addition of Cu^{II} whilst the rest of the cations do not modify or increase the fluorescent emission. Moreover, addition of up to 2 equiv. of Cu^{II} also modifies the absorption spectrum. The Job's plot of the UV-Vis data yielded a 1 : 1 stoichiometry for its Cu^{II} complex.

Ghosh *et al.* reported a simple tripodal shaped chemosensor (**11**) for metal ions¹⁵. In CH_3CN containing 0.04% DMSO, upon excitation at 370 nm, the chemosensor exhibited structured emission centred at

418 nm, which increased to a significant extent upon complexation of Cu^{II} . The other metal ions except Zn^{2+} and Hg^{2+} examined in this study did not exhibit any marked change in emission under a similar condition. Although Cu^{2+} ion showed strong interaction with (**11**), Zn^{2+} and Hg^{2+} ions exhibited moderate binding.

Jang's group synthesized a novel benzimidazole-based, anthracene-coupled fluorescent receptor (**12**) capable of recognizing and estimating the concentrations of Fe^{3+} in semi-aqueous solution by ratiometric estimation¹⁶. The sensor can be made highly selective for Fe^{3+} over other metal ions by changing the solvent composition.

Ghosh *et al.* reported a benzimidazole based chemosensor (**13**), derived from L-valine¹⁷. The chemosensor effectively recognises Hg^{2+} ion in the open cleft in CH_3CN containing 0.2% DMSO by exhibiting significant enhancement in fluorescence emission. The steric isopropyl groups in (**13**) play the key role in the selectivity. The ensemble of (**13**). Hg^{2+} also showed the fluorescence sensing of L-cysteine, homocysteine, and glutathione over the other amino acids with no thiol group in aq. DMSO (DMSO : H_2O , 4 : 1, v/v).

Luxami *et al.* reported a probe (**14**) selectively bind with Zn^{2+} ions at pH 7.0 (10 mM, HEPES) in CH_3CN - H_2O (4 : 1) and give a new emission band at 490 nm¹⁸. These can estimate 20 nM Zn^{2+} ions as the lowest detection limit. The determination of Zn^{2+} ions by probe (**14**) is not interfered by the presence of other metal ions expects in the case of Cu^{2+} causes only the fluorescence quenching. In acetonitrile, the addition of different concentrations of Cu^{2+} (2 mM, 5 mM, 10

mM) and a fixed amount of F^- (25 mM) to a solution of **(14)** (0.25 mM, CH_3CN) elaborates Cu^{2+} ion concentration dependent NOR, INH and AND Boolean operators with three distinct emission channels at 585, 515 and 400 nm, respectively.

Dessingou's group showed the benzimidazole containing moiety **(15)** act as a selective "turn-on" fluorescence response toward Ag^+ ¹⁹. The selectivity of **(15)** has been explored in aqueous methanol, resulting in selective 8-fold switch-on fluorescence response toward Ag^+ among 14 different transition, alkali, and alkaline earth metal ions studied. The complexation of Ag^+ by **(15)** has been addressed by ESI-MS, 1H NMR, and UV-Vis spectra. Microstructural features of **(15)** and its Ag^+ complex have been measured by AFM and TEM. The morphological features of **(15)** alone and **(15)** in the presence of Ag^+ differ dramatically both in shape and size, and the ion induces the formation of chains owing to its coordinating ability toward benzimidazole. Further, the *in situ* [Ag^+ -**(15)**] complex was titrated against 20 naturally occurring amino acids and found that this complex acts as a secondary recognition ensemble toward Cys, Asp, and Glu by switch-off fluorescence.

Singh *et al.* developed a new benzimidazole-based receptor **(16)** with potential functional groups for excited state proton transfer (ESPT) through ketoenol tautomerism²⁰. The enol form of the receptor selectively recognizes Zn^{2+} , allowing it to be used as a ratiometric fluorescence sensor in DMSO/ CH_3CN (1 : 9, v/v). The binding event triggers a blue-shifted band through the modulation of charge transfer transitions. The sensor is applicable for recognizing Zn^{2+} in the cytoplasm of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*.

An imine-linked, benzimidazole-based sensor **(17)**, reported by Jang *et al.*²¹, was used for chromogenic recognition of Mg^{2+} and fluorescent recognition of Cr^{3+} . Addition of Mg^{2+} to a solution of **(17)** in CH_3CN -HEPES buffer (8 : 2, v/v, pH 7.0) led to a stepwise decrease in absorbance at 400 nm and an increase at 350 nm with a clear isosbestic point at 385 nm. Cr^{3+} binding with sensor **(17)** caused a change in the fluorescence spectra of **(17)** with quenching at 415

nm and enhancement at 475 nm. In the absence of Cr^{3+} , the enol form of **(17)** was in equilibrium with its keto tautomer in the excited state. The modulation of the fluorescence spectrum of **(17)** with the addition of Cr^{3+} ions was due to the formation of a stable Cr^{3+} complex with the keto form of **(17)**. In addition, **(17)** was applicable for staining the cytoplasm of microbial cells enriched with Cr^{3+} .

Two Zn^{2+} ion selective fluorescent probes **(18a)** and **(18b)** based on a coumarin Schiff base were designed and synthesized by Guo *et al.* on the basis of C=N isomerization mechanism²². Both the X-ray crystal structure of the zinc complex and the Job's plots showed a 1 : 1 probe- Zn^{2+} ion identification with high selectivity and sensitivity. The probe **(18a)** was also used to image intracellular Zn^{2+} ions in MCF-7 cells with a good performance.

Interestingly, imidazo-benzocrown ether-based ionophores **(19-21)** bearing arylthienyl and bithienyl π -conjugated bridges have been evaluated as fluorimetric sensors for Cu^{II} and Pd^{II} ions (Table 1). Moreover, systems **(20)** and **(21)** have also proved to be efficient sensors for basic anions such as F^- , due to changes in emission after deprotonation of the imidazole NH by the F^- ion²³.

Molina *et al.* reported a redox, chromogenic, and fluorescent chemosensor molecule **(22)** based on a deazapurine ring which could selectively detect aqueous Pb^{2+} in acetonitrile over other metal ions. Probe **(22)** showed a redox shift ($E_{1/2} = 0.15$ V of the Fe^{II}/Fe^{III} redox couple) with a color change from the colorless to orange, and an emission change of 620-fold, with an unprecedented detection limit of $2.7 \mu g L^{-1}$ ²⁴. The signal transduction occurs via a reversible CHEF with this inherent quenching metal ion.

A mercury non-sulfur and simple fluorescent chemosensor **(23)** based on the benzimidazole group and quinoline group as the fluorescence signal group has been designed and synthesized by Chen's group²⁵. The receptor could instantly detect the Hg^{2+} cation over other cations by fluorescence spectroscopy in $H_2O/DMSO$ (1 : 9, v/v) solution with specific selectivity and high sensitivity with the fluorescence color change

of the solution from blue to colorless only after the addition of Hg^{2+} in aqueous media. Moreover, further study demonstrates that the detection limit on the fluorescence response of the sensor to Hg^{2+} is $9.56 \times 10^{-9} \text{ M}$. Test strips based on **(23)** were fabricated, which could act as convenient and efficient Hg^{2+} test kits. Thus, the probe should have potential applications in an aqueous environment for the monitoring of mercury.

Zhang *et al.* reported a fluorescent sensor **(24)** based on benzimidazo[2,1-*a*]benz[*de*]isoquinoline-7-one which can be used as chemosensor for various metal ions²⁶. By the introduction of *N,N*-bis(pyridin-2-ylmethyl)-ethane-1,2-diamine as an electron-donating receptor, chemosensor **(24)** exhibited weak fluorescence due to fluorescence quenching by the PET (photoinduced electron transfer) process from the lone pair electrons on the nitrogen atom to the fluorophore. On the other hand, the receptor may have a strong binding ability toward metal ions due to its multiple coordinating groups. After binding with metal ions, a large chelation-enhanced fluorescence (CHEF) effect would be observed because the chelation abrogated the PET process giving it possible to be used as a fluorescent sensor in pure water.

Mashraqui *et al.* synthesized a chemosensor **(25)** in two steps from readily accessible 2,6-bis(2-benzimidazole)pyridine. Photophysical studies revealed that of the several metal ions examined, biologically and environmentally significant Zn^{2+} exhibited highly selective emission wavelength shifts under the buffer condition²⁷. In contrast to Zn^{2+} , the coordinatively competing and toxic Cd^{2+} elicited less remarkable optical responses as evidenced by its two order of magnitude lower stability constant compared to that of Zn^{2+} . Moreover, metal ions, viz. Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Hg^{2+} and Pb^{2+} exhibited insignificant optical perturbations even in concentrations far exceeding Zn^{2+} . Clearly, the probe has the attributes to selectively target Zn^{2+} by ratiometric analysis under buffer conditions.

A rhodamine-benzimidazole based chemosensor **(26)** was designed and prepared by Li's group for Fe^{3+} via

opening of the spiro-ring to give fluorescent and colored species. **(26)** exhibited high selectivity and excellent sensitivity in both absorbance and fluorescence detection of Fe^{3+} in aqueous solution with comparatively wide pH range (5.8–7.4)²⁸. The detection limit of this newly developed probe was shown to be up to $2.74 \mu\text{M}$. The reversibility establishes the potential of both probes as chemosensors for Fe^{3+} detection. Fluorescence imaging experiments of Fe^{3+} in living MGC803 cells demonstrated its value of practical applications in biological systems. It also displayed enhanced fluorescence intensities and clear color changes upon recognition. Moreover, fast response (in 10 s) and neutral aqueous medium made it possible to be practical application for Fe^{3+} ions. The probe could be applied in biological systems for the detection of Fe^{3+} through confocal laser scanning microscopy experiments.

On the basis of fluorescence resonance energy transfer (FRET) from benzimidazole to a rhodamine moiety, another rhodamine-benzimidazole conjugate **(27)** ratiometric fluorescent probe has been designed and synthesized by Goswami *et al.*²⁹. **(27)** selectively binds to Cu^{2+} , showing visually observable changes in absorption and emission behavior, and demonstrates an effective intracellular Cu^{2+} imaging ability, allowing it to function as a cytoplasm marker.

Tang's group reported a phenylbenzimidazole derivatized sensor **(28)** that behaves as a ratiometric fluorescent receptor for Zn^{2+} in water has been described³⁰. In HEPES buffer at pH 7.4, sensor **(28)** displays a weak fluorescence emission band at 367 nm. Upon addition of Zn^{2+} , the emission intensity at 367 nm is decreased, concomitantly, a new emission band centered at 426 nm is developed, thus facilitates a ratiometric Zn^{2+} sensing behavior. Sensor **(28)** binds Zn^{2+} through a 1 : 1 binding stoichiometry with high selectivity over other metal cations. Sensor displays a linear response to Zn^{2+} concentration from 0 to $6.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, sensor **(28)** also exhibits high sensitivity to Zn^{2+} with a detection limit of $3.31 \times 10^{-7} \text{ M}$.

Li and co-workers reported an optical and fluorometric pH sensor **(29)** by attaching pH sensitive group

benzimidazole at the 2-position of borondipyrromethene³¹. Due to the electron-donor effect, benzimidazole group caused obvious bathochromic shift in the absorption and fluorescence spectra. Upon protonation, the solution exhibited drastic blue-shifted absorption and enhanced fluorescence, and the color changed from yellow to green simultaneously. The sensing mechanism was elucidated by quantum chemistry calculation approach. Cell experiments were carried out to verify the compound could selectively locate in the acidic lysosome. These results indicated the benzimidazole-BODIPY could be used as an optical and “off-on” fluorescent pH indicator.

A highly sensitive and selective benzimidazole based colourimetric chemosensor (**30**) for the efficient detection of Ni²⁺ has been reported by Mondal *et al.*³². The synthesized chemosensor (**30**) is highly efficient in detecting Ni²⁺ over other metal ions that commonly coexist with Ni²⁺ in physiological and environmental samples. Probe (**30**) also shows distinct color change from orange yellow to blue visible under the “naked-eye” due to specific binding with Ni²⁺. This color change corresponds to a large red shift of the UV-Vis spectrum from 403 nm to 600 nm with a distinct isosbestic point at around 500 nm. The cation sensing property of the receptor (**30**) has been examined by UV-Vis spectroscopy. Electronic structure of its Ni²⁺ complex and sensing mechanism has been interpreted by DFT and TDDFT calculations.

Naphthalene benzimidazole conjugate (**31**) bearing a hydroxyl group was synthesized by Nandhakumar *et al.* Its binding properties towards various metal ions were examined and it showed a high selectivity and sensitivity towards Al³⁺ ions in CH₃CN-H₂O solution (1 : 1, v/v, HEPES 50 mM, pH 7.0)³³. The sensor was designed in such a way that the naphthalene acts as fluorophore which is covalently attached to the benzimidazole scaffold which contains the heterocyclic nitrogen atoms. The recognition processes follows a photo induced electron transfer (PET) mechanism assisted with the restricted intramolecular C-C single bond rotation and are scarcely influenced by other coexisting metal ions. In addition, determination of Al³⁺ in a

variety of sewage water samples was also determined. These authors synthesized a quinoline benzimidazole-conjugate (**32**) for the highly selective detection of Zn^{II} both by colorimetry and fluorimetry³⁴. Probe (**32**) senses Zn²⁺ over other cations as fluorescence “off-on” behaviour in HEPES-buffered CH₃CN/H₂O (1 : 1, v/v, pH 7.0) solution. A possible mechanism is proposed based on the inhibition of PET and intramolecular restricted torsional rotation through the C-C single bond between the quinoline benzimidazole-conjugate. This probe has been reported as a useful chemosensor to detect Zn²⁺ ions in much real sample analysis. Singh’s group synthesized a novel receptor and multianalyte fluorescent probe with benzimidazole moieties in a tripodal framework (**33**)³⁵. The receptor displays rarely observed metal specific fluorescence enhancement at two different wavelengths. The receptor was investigated for the simultaneous analysis of Cu²⁺ and Fe³⁺ and successfully quantified the ions without interference over a wide concentration range.

Recently reported some benzimidazole derivatives having quinazoline moiety (**34-42**) (viz. Table 1) showed metal sensing property either by formation of chelating environment for incoming metal ions. Interestingly, in some cases this type of compounds ligate the metal ions selectively through solvent/metal ion assisted 1,5-σ tropic shift (**34-42**). The first example where reported a probe 2,6-bis(5,6-dihydrobenzo-[4,5]imidazo[1,2-c]quinazolin-6-yl)-4-methylphenol (**34**) as a selective and sensitive fluorescent probe for Zn²⁺ in a HEPES buffer (50 mM, DMSO : water = 1 : 9 (v/v), pH 7.2) at 25 °C³⁶, where formation of the zinc complex needs a [1,5] sigmatropic-type shift of the secondary N-H proton of the probe (**34**) prior to binding with Zn²⁺ to form a Schiff base structure evidenced by the solid state crystal structure. The selective enhancement of fluorescence intensity in presence of Zn²⁺ is due to the formation of dinuclear Zn²⁺ complex [Zn₂(C₃₅H₂₅N₆O)(OH)(NO₃)₂(H₂O)] with increase of fluorescence quantum yield of the chemosensor by more than 12-fold in the presence of 2 equiv. of the zinc ion. Here, upon complexation, the

lone pair of electrons on the N atom of the organic moiety is no longer available for PET, leading to fluorescence enhancement. This probe is also potent to identify the distribution of Zn^{2+} ions in the living cells (A375 and HT-29) using fluorescence microscopy. Similar type compound (**35**) have also reported as a highly selective ratiometric fluorescent sensor for Fe^{2+} at pH 4.0–5.0 and Fe^{3+} at pH 6.5–8.0 in acetonitrile-HEPES buffer (1/4) (v/v) medium³⁷. The probe is a “naked-eye” chemosensor for two states of iron and is efficient for detecting *in vitro* Fe^{3+} ions in the biological organelles by developing a fluorescence images. According to the same group, probe (**36**) was rationally illustrated as a highly selective cell-permeable ratiometric fluorescent chemosensor for ReO^{V} ion in acetonitrile : water = 9 : 1 (v/v) at 25 °C³⁸. The fluorescence quantum yield of the chemosensor (**36**) was only 0.198 at 410 nm, and it increased more than 3-fold in the presence of 2 equiv. of the ReO^{V} ion at 478 nm with almost no interferences of other metal ions and relevant anions. In another example a benzimidazole based fluorescent Cr^{3+} receptor, (**37**) was reported³⁹. The sensor is efficient for detection of Cr^{3+} *in vitro*, developing a good image of the biological organelles. Recently there is example of two structurally modified quinazoline derivatives (**38** and **39**) act as highly selective chemosensor for Al^{3+} ions in $\text{DMSO-H}_2\text{O}$ (1 : 9, v/v) over the other competitive metal ions⁴⁰. Both the probes show a red shifted fluorescence after addition of Al^{3+} ions and later the further fluorescence enhancement is due to chelation enhanced fluorescence (CHEF) through inhibition of photoinduced electron transfer (PET). (**38**) detects Al^{3+} ions as low as 9 nM whereas (**39**) can detect Al^{3+} ions as low as 1.48 nM in 100 mM HEPES buffer (water/DMSO, 9/1, v/v) at biological pH within a very short responsive time (15–20 s). This two non cytotoxic probe can efficiently detect the intercellular distribution of Al^{3+} ions in living cells under fluorescence microscope to exhibit its sensible applications in the biological systems. In this context Chellappa *et al.* reported a ratiometric chemosensor, 6-imidazo-2-yl-5,6-dihydrobenzo[4,5]imidazo[1,2-c]quinazoline (**40**) selective for

Al^{3+} ions as low as 5.3×10^{-7} M in aqueous-DMSO⁴¹. A highly fluorescent and efficient ratiometric “turn-on” probe for Hg^{2+} and Al^{3+} based on quinazoline (**41**) has been designed and synthesized by Pandey and co-authors⁴². Limit of detection (LOD) and association constants revealed its superior binding affinity and sensitivity toward Hg^{2+} over Al^{3+} . Paul *et al.* reported structurally characterised quinazoline functionalized benzimidazole-based fluorogenic chemosensor (**42**) as a highly selective colorimetric and fluorescence sensor for Cu^{2+} ions in $\text{DMF}/0.02$ M HEPES (1 : 1, v/v, pH 7.4) medium⁴³. Again, this copper(II) complex acts as a metal based highly selective and sensitive chemosensor for S^{2-} ions even in the presence of other commonly coexisting anions such in $\text{DMF}/0.02$ M HEPES (1 : 1, v/v, pH 7.4) medium due to the liberation of probe (**42**). Quantification analysis indicates that these receptors, (**42**) and its Cu^{II} complex, can detect Cu^{2+} ions and S^{2-} ions upto 1.6×10^{-9} M and 5.2×10^{-6} M, respectively.

Chemosensors for anions :

The benzimidazole based organic moieties of judicial designs are also effective to detect the anions selectively. Jang and co-workers reported a compound comprise of three benzimidazole units connected by a tripodal 2,2',2''-trioxiethylamine linker (**43**) which behaves as a good I^- ion selective chemosensor in $\text{CH}_3\text{CN}/\text{water}$ (9 : 1) buffered with HEPES at neutral pH based on quenching mechanism⁴⁴. The ^1H NMR titration with iodide showed that this anion is fundamentally bound by the NH protons of the benzimidazole moiety.

The receptors (**44** and **45**), reported by Jang and co-workers, in which one or two 2-aminobenzimidazole groups are connected to an anthracene ring are significant in the field of molecular recognition of anions⁴⁵. Receptor (**44**) displayed strong fluorescence emission in CH_3CN , which is quenched with the addition of halide, AcO^- and H_2PO_4^- anions. The quenching mechanism has been attributed to a photoinduced electron transfer (PET) process. Compound (**45**), bearing two benzimidazole units, presents similar results and selectivities, though higher association constants were

found and a preference for AcO^- over F^- was also observed.

Jang's group synthesized a fluorescent receptor (**46**) bearing benzimidazole moiety as recognition sites (viz. Table 2)⁴⁶. The recognition behaviour of the receptor towards various anions has been evaluated in CH_3CN . The receptor showed ratiometric fluorescent changes only with CH_3COO^- , and it showed no significant response to any of other anions such as Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , HSO_4^- , NO_3^- , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COO}^-$ and H_2PO_4^- .

Lin and co-workers published a chromogenic "naked-eye" anions receptor (**47**) having a dinitrobenzimidazole unit connected to a phenol donating group in an aqueous media⁴⁷. The presence of the nitro groups increases the polarity of the molecule, making it more suitable for chromogenic detection and increases the acidity of the NH group of benzimidazole. Addition of F^- to a solution of compound (**47**) induces a clear color change that is not observable with other halide anions. The fluoride ion binds strongly with (**47**) because of its highest electro-negativity and smallest size among all of the anions being investigated here. In the UV-Vis spectrum of the complex formed, a new charge-transfer band appears which is responsible for this colour change. The ^1H NMR study carried out to investigate the coordination modes illustrates that the NH group of the benzimidazole and the phenolic OH are responsible for the F^- ion coordination.

Within the concept of two-arms receptors, Jang and co-workers synthesized two isophthalamide receptors containing benzimidazole (**48a**) and nitrobenzimidazole (**45b**) units⁴⁸ and a 1,3-bisurea bearing two benzimidazole moieties (**49**)⁴⁹. Compound (**45b**) experiences a bathochromic shift of the UV-Vis bands with the addition of F^- and AcO^- anions in $\text{CH}_3\text{CN}/\text{DMSO}$ (99 : 1) observable by "naked-eye", while the rest of the anions tested do not cause any important variations. When the same titrations are carried out on the related receptor (**48a**), it exhibited no change in the absorption spectrum upon addition of any of the anions assayed. In the case of (**49**), after addition of 5 equiv. of the sodium salt of a large variety of anions, only the

phosphate anion quenches the fluorescence of the receptor in a DMSO/water mixture while the other anions do not modify importantly the fluorescence emission. A PET quenching process has been addressed to explain the fluorescence changes. The ^1H NMR titration of the receptor with phosphate exhibits an upfield shifting of the thiourea and benzimidazole NH protons involved in the recognition process that points to the presence of hydrogen bonds in the neat receptor that are stronger than in the complex. The popularity of the tweezer-like structures for anion recognition is again demonstrated with the preparation of two molecules bearing a phenanthroline, two imide and two benzimidazole moieties as receptor units⁵⁰. Lin's group reported two novel and neutral benzimidazole derivatives bearing a 1,10-phenanthroline fluorophore (**50**) as anion receptors based on "turn-on" and "turn-off" fluorescence responses to various anions in DMSO solution. In the process of anions binding, there were two different fluorescent responses in presence of anions : a quenching of the fluorescence emission for F^- and AcO^- ions and an enhancement of the fluorescence emission for Cl^- , Br^- and I^- ions. Two different luminescent mechanisms of the receptors resulting from various anions were exploited to rationalize quenching and enhancement of the fluorescence emission : a photo-induced electronic transfer mechanism (PET) and the increase of the rigidity of the host molecules, respectively. In particular, chloride could be recognized selectively from the anions tested according to changes of fluorescence spectrum.

Tomapatanaget and co-workers synthesized anion receptors (**51** and **52**) fabricated from the imidazole unit and anthraquinone moieties. ^1H NMR spectroscopy and UV-Vis titrations in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ and DMSO, respectively, showed that both receptors underwent deprotonation at the NH moiety of the amide-anthraquinone unit in the presence of basic anions such as F^- and AcO^- ⁵¹. These phenomena gave a dramatic color change due to charge transfer transition corresponding to the shift of λ_{max} from 371 nm to 489 nm. Redox chemistry of (**51**) and (**52**) in the presence of anions (F^- , Cl^- , AcO^- , BzO^- , and H_2PO_4^-) using cy-

clic voltammetry showed the different cyclic voltammogram (CV) responses upon addition of various anions. In the case of (51) with various anions, the CV changes are dependent on the basic strength of anions in order of $F^- > AcO^-$, $BzO^- > H_2PO_4^- > Cl^-$, Br^- . Interestingly, the CV responses of (52) with $H_2PO_4^-$ exhibited the most significant changes. Thus, (52) has an excellent electrochemical selectivity toward $H_2PO_4^-$ ion.

Ghosh *et al.* designed and synthesized an anthracene-appended benzimidazolium-based receptor (53). The receptor shows selective recognition of iodide in the excited state by exhibiting quenching of emission of anthracene⁵². In the ground state, receptor shows different selectivity and prefers to bind bromide with higher binding constant value as established from NMR titration experiment. Other anions in the study indicated weak or no interaction. Hydrogen bonding and charge-charge interactions are the forces responsible for strong binding. The interaction properties of the new receptor were evaluated by ¹H NMR, UV-Vis

and fluorescence spectroscopic methods. The anthracene-linked bis(benzimidazole)diamide (54) has also been described as a simple receptor for the selective detection of metal ions and organic sulfonic acids⁵³. Differences in the monomer/excimer ratio of fluorescent emission of the anthracene moieties were used to detect the presence of diverse organic acids in $CHCl_3$ and CH_3CN /water (4 : 1) solutions. The change in emission was considerable in the presence of methanesulfonic acid and *p*-toluenesulfonic acid while the addition of acetic, mandelic or trifluoroacetic acids less perturbed the emission of receptor (54) due to the protonation of host by the most acidic sulfonic acids and the formation of different ion pairs. Changes in the absorption spectrum correlate well with the fluorescence results. Moreover, metal complexation was studied in CH_3CN and addition of increasing amounts of transition metal cations decreases both the monomer and the excimer emission, although the effect on the excimer band is more pronounced. Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions cause the most marked changes in comparison to the other transition metals.

Table 2. Benzimidazole based chemosensors selective for anions

Table-2 (contd.)

(49)

(50a) R=H
(50b) R=CH₃

(51)

(52)

(53)

(54)

(55)

(56)

(57)

(58)

(59)

(60)

(73)

R=H and OH

(74)

(75)

(76)

(77)

(78)

Ghosh *et al.* designed and synthesized a new anthracene-coupled benzimidazolium-based tripodal, tricationic fluorescent chemosensor (**55**)⁵⁴. Receptor exhibits high degree of selectivity towards H_2PO_4^- in CH_3CN through anion-induced quenching of emission along with the formation of a weak excimer complex in the excited states. Furthermore, receptor shows selective sensing of ATP over ADP and AMP by exhibiting an increase in emission in aqueous CH_3CN ($\text{CH}_3\text{CN} : \text{H}_2\text{O}$, 3 : 2, v/v). The electrostatic charge-charge interaction along with both conventional ($\text{NH}\cdots\text{X}$; $\text{X}=\text{O}$, halides) and unconventional ($\text{C}^+\text{H}\cdots\text{X}$; $\text{X}=\text{O}$, halides) hydrogen bonding between the host and the guest molecule synergistically interplays in the complexation. The anion-binding properties of receptor were understood by ^1H NMR, UV-Vis and fluorescence spectroscopic methods.

Eichen *et al.* reported cyclo[2]benzimidazole (**56**) as a new host for anions that turns on its luminescence up to 150-fold upon binding⁵⁵. Photoexcited cyclo[2]benzimidazole undergoes an efficient non-ra-

diative deactivation through an excited-state intramolecular protontransfer (ESIPT) mechanism. Upon binding an anion, the ESIPT pathway is blocked, resulting in an increase in the luminescence efficiency.

Lee and co-workers synthesized a novel 1,3,5-substituted triethylbenzene derivative (**57**) with a 2-aminobenzimidazole moiety as a binding and signaling subunit⁵⁶. The sensor was tested in a buffered $\text{CH}_3\text{CN}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99 : 1, v/v) solution and found to be selective for iodide as demonstrated by the photophysical properties obtained through UV-Vis absorption and fluorescence spectroscopy analyses.

A simple CN^- sensor (**58**) bearing a naphthol and an imine group was designed and synthesized by Zhang's group, which showed both a colorimetric and a fluorescence "turn-on" response for cyanide ions in aqueous solution⁵⁷. The probe shows an immediate visible change in color from yellow to orange which then becomes colorless followed by a final change to pink, when cyanide is added; these color changes can be readily observed visually. The mechanism for the

cyanide ion sensing was established by using ^1H NMR and FT-IR spectroscopy and mass spectrometry. Moreover, test strips based on the sensor were fabricated, which could act as a convenient and efficient CN^- test kit.

Zhang *et al.* reported a series of novel acridine derived bis-benzimidazolium macrocyclic fluorescent sensors (**59** and **60**)⁵⁸. X-Ray crystal structures demonstrated the self-assembly behavior of these cyclophanes in the solid state driven by hydrogen bond and π - π interactions. Anion binding studies of these sensors revealed a significant effect of the macrocyclic size and rigidity for H_2PO_4^- sensing via the obvious "turn-on" as well as bathochromic-shift in fluorescence emission. Different cavity size or rigidity of the sensors showed different bathochromic-shifts of 36 to 126 nm in fluorescence emission induced by H_2PO_4^- , which resulted in significant color changes of fluorescence from blue to orange red, orange, green and blue-green respectively. The unique fluorescence response toward H_2PO_4^- may be attributed to H_2PO_4^- -induced assembly of sensors forming the excimer between two acridine rings to a different extent.

A series of pyridine-coupled benzimidazolium-based receptors (**61**, **62** and **63**) have been designed and synthesized by Ghosh *et al.* In the series, only receptor (**61**) is structurally appealing in the selective recognition of H_2PO_4^- in CHCl_3 as well as in CH_3CN over a series of other anions⁵⁹. The ratiometric change in emission with a triplet band at 420 nm is the distinctive feature of selective recognition of H_2PO_4^- in CHCl_3 . In CH_3CN , a "turn-on" response is selectively observed. Binding studies have been carried out using fluorescence, UV-Vis, ^1H NMR and ^{31}P NMR spectroscopic techniques. Experimental results have been correlated with the theoretical findings.

Molina *et al.* reported a benzimidazole based receptor (**64**) which senses aqueous H_2PO_4^- and $\text{HP}_2\text{O}_7^{3-}$ anions through different channels in DMSO. A red-shift of the emission band with an important chelation enhanced fluorescence effect and a large cathodic shift

of the ferrocene. The recognition event has also been studied by ^1H NMR spectroscopy. It is worth mentioning that a series of ruthenium complexes containing bis-benzimidazole derivatives have been identified as able to target mitochondria and induce caspase-dependent apoptosis in cancer cells through superoxide overproduction⁶⁰. Following with the family of ruthenium complexes, Ye and co-workers prepared mononuclear complexes with 2,2-bisbenzimidazole and the corresponding 4,4'-bismethylated ligand⁶¹. In a similar way as in the aforementioned complexes, compounds (**65**) and (**66**) experienced successive deprotonations in CH_3CN with F^- and AcO^- that were followed by UV-Vis, emission spectroscopy, ^1H NMR and electrochemical methods. Additionally, a strong hydrogen bond coordination of the less basic anions is observed in emission spectroscopy and ^1H NMR experiments. A theoretical paper published by Zhang and co-workers studies the coordination/deprotonation process in this sort of ruthenium bis(benzimidazol-2-yl)imidazole complexes⁶². Computational results, obtained with (TD)-DFT methods in the Gaussian09 program, support a proton transfer process for the spectroscopic and electrochemical changes experienced in these compounds.

Liu and co-workers reported a fluorescence sensor (**67**) bearing NH and OH subunits displayed a highly selective and sensitive recognition property for fluoride over other anions⁶³. Fluoride-driven ESPT, poorly used in anion recognition and sensing, was suggested to be responsible for the fluorescence enhancement with a blue shift of 35 nm in the emission spectrum. Singh *et al.* reported a Co^{3+} complex of similar type of benzimidazole-based probe (**68**) and evaluated as a sensor for I^- and HSO_4^- in aqueous media⁶⁴. The complex showed electrochemical changes with I^- over other anions, whereas it had a ratiometric response towards HSO_4^- ions in UV-Vis spectroscopic study even in the presence of other anions.

A simple, tailor made receptor (**69**) based on azo dye featuring with benzimidazole unit with hybrid

-OH and -NH binding sites was synthesized and characterized by Singh's group. The addition of CN^- , AcO^- , F^- , and H_2PO_4^- in acetonitrile solution of (**69**) resulted in a large bathochromic shift from 315 nm to 470 nm allowing "naked-eye" color change from colorless to orange⁶⁵. Anion sensing characteristics were determined using visual inspection, UV-Vis and ^1H NMR spectroscopy pointing toward the improved chromogenic ability after introduction of -N=N- group in the azo dye (**69**). The mechanism of anion binding with receptor (**69**) showed 1 : 2 (**69**/Anion) and the association constants were found in the order of $\text{AcO}^- > \text{CN}^- > \text{F}^- > \text{H}_2\text{PO}_4^-$.

1,3-Bis(5,6-dimethyl-1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazol-2-yl)benzene (**70**) a neutral tridentate ligand, is synthesized and employed as a chemosensor by Iyer *et al.* for the detection of different anions with highest affinity for fluoride⁶⁶. The detection ability of this ligand (**70**) is confirmed using UV-Vis spectroscopy, fluorescence spectroscopy and ^1H NMR techniques. Anion binding studies using ^1H NMR and fluorescence spectroscopy revealed that (**70**) exhibits high selectivity for fluoride over other anions.

A benzimidazole-based compound (**71**) built on the piperazine motif has been designed and synthesized by Ghosh *et al.*⁶⁷. The chemosensor (**71**) is highly selective and sensitive towards ATP over ADP and AMP in $\text{CH}_3\text{CN}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 : 1, v/v, using 10 mM HEPES buffer, pH 6.4) as evidenced by the significant change in emission. Furthermore, sensor (**71**) is cell permeable and can detect the presence of ATP in Human cervical cancer cells (HeLa).

Samanta's group synthesized a new dibenzimidazole diimine sensor (**72**) for selective detection of acetate ion⁶⁸. Significant "naked-eye" recognized color change of (**72**) solution from light yellow to pink upon addition of only acetate ion is accompanied with near infrared (NIR) emission exploiting excited state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT).

Sen Gupta *et al.* synthesized ESIPT based benzimidazole derivative and investigated their photophysical

behaviour towards various anions⁶⁹. The probe (**73**) has been used for selective estimation of F^- ions as compared to other anions and signaled the binding event through formation of new absorption band at 360 nm and emission band at 420 nm. The probe (**73**) showed fluorescence behaviour towards fluoride ions through hydrogen bonding interactions and restricted the ESIPT emission at 540 nm from OH to nitrogen of benzimidazole moiety to release its enol emission at 420 nm.

In another work Sen Gupta *et al.* synthesized excited state intramolecular proton transfer based benzimidazole derivative having push-pull effect has been synthesized and investigated their photophysical behavior towards various anions⁷⁰. The probe (**74**) has been used for selective estimation of F^- and CN^- anions and signaled the binding event through formation of new absorption band at 465 nm. The probe (**74**) opens different emission channels at 425 nm in the presence of CN^- ions and two new emission bands at 435 nm and 365 nm in case of F^- ions. The probe (**74**) behaved as chemodosimeter for CN^- ions which have been proved by ^1H NMR and whereas fluoride caused hydrogen bonding interactions with probe (**74**) and restricted the ESIPT emission at 505 nm from OH to nitrogen of benzimidazole moiety to release its enol emission. The differential behaviour of F^- ions and CN^- has been confirmed through DFT calculations.

A sensitive fluorescent probe, 2,2'-bisbenzimidazole (**75**), for CN^- has been developed by Liu and co-workers. This structurally simple receptor displays great selectivity for the cyanide anion over other common inorganic anions in an aqueous environment⁷¹. In addition further study demonstrates the lower detection of the fluorescence response of the sensor to CN^- is in 10^{-9} mol/L range. Thus, the present probe should be applicable as a practical system for the monitoring of cyanide concentrations in aqueous samples.

In recent study two new 2-(2-aminophenyl)benzimidazole-based HSO_4^- ion selective receptors, (**76**) and (**77**) have synthesized^{72a}. Both receptors (**76** and **77**) behave as highly selective chemosensor for HSO_4^-

ions at biological pH in ethanol-water HEPES buffer (1/5) (v/v) medium over other anions. Theoretical and experimental studies showed that the emission efficiency of the receptors was tuned successfully through single point to ratiometric detection by employing the substituent effects. Using 3s method the LOD for HSO_4^- ions were found to be very low. The structure property relationship of the bisulphate ensemble was established in another work reported by the same authors^{72b}. Here quinazoline based receptor (**78**) selectively senses HSO_4^- ions of nanomolar region in 0.1 M HEPES buffer (ethanol-water : 1/5, v/v) at biological pH over other competitive ions through the proton transfer followed by hydrogen bond formation and subsequent anion coordination.

Benzimidazole based for both cations and anions :

In the field of both recognition of cations and anions the Cu^{2+} and cyanide successive recognition feature was examined by Tang and co-workers. A benzimidazole-based imine linked sensor (**79**) (viz. Table 3) exhibits highly selective and sensitive recognition properties to Cu^{2+} in $\text{CH}_3\text{OH}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1/1, v/v, HEPES 10 mM, pH 7.0) solution with a 1 : 1 binding stoichiometry⁷³. The *in situ* prepared Cu^{2+} complex solution displays high selectivity to cyanide through Cu^{2+} displacement approach and possesses excellent tolerance to other common interference anions. The detection limits of sensor (**79**) to Cu^{2+} and Cu^{2+} complex to cyanide were estimated to be 1.82×10^{-8} M and 1.62×10^{-6} M, respectively. This Cu^{2+} and cyanide successive recognition feature of sensor (**79**) makes it a potential utility for Cu^{2+} and cyanide detection in aqueous media.

Saluja's group synthesized a benzimidazole-based imine linked receptor (**80**) for fluorescent recognition of Cu^{2+} in a $\text{CH}_3\text{CN}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (8 : 2, v/v) solvent system⁷⁴. The sensor was highly sensitive and selective for Cu^{2+} detection at low detection limit. The Cu^{2+} complex with the receptor acted as a sensor for a phosphate anion and the phosphate recognition event restored the fluorescence intensity of the receptor.

Das *et al.* synthesized and characterized a benzimidazole-based tripodal fluorescence derivative (**81**). Combining (**81**) with Cu^{2+} shows excellent selectivity toward sulfide anions⁷⁵. The binding stoichiometry of (**81**) with Cu^{2+} is established by Jobs' plot analysis and mass spectral evidence. The initial fluorescence of (**81**) is lost on complexation with Cu^{2+} and is regained in presence of sulfide. The "off-on" behavior of (**81**) is studied by fluorescence, UV/Vis and mass spectroscopic methods.

To realize highly selective relay recognition of Cu^{2+} and sulfide ions, a simple benzimidazole-based fluorescent chemosensor (**82**) was designed and synthesized by Tang's group⁷⁶. Sensor (**82**) displays rapid, highly selective and sensitive recognition to Cu^{2+} in 100% water solution at pH 6.0. The *in situ* generated Cu^{2+} complex solution exhibit a fast response and high selectivity toward sulfide anion via Cu^{2+} displacement approach. The detection limits of sensor (**82**) to Cu^{2+} and Cu^{2+} complex to sulfide anion were estimated to be 3.5×10^{-7} M and 1.35×10^{-6} M, respectively. Proof-of-concept experiment results demonstrate that sensor (**82**) has potential utilities for Cu^{2+} and sulfide ion concentration evaluation in real water samples. This successive recognition features of sensor (**82**) makes it has a potential utility for Cu^{2+} and sulfide anion detection in water.

The 2-(2'-aminophenyl)benzimidazole (2-APBI) derivatized fluorescent sensor (**83**) that also behaves relay recognition of Cu^{2+} and S^{2-} in water solution (pH 7.4) has been developed by the same authors⁷⁷. Sensor (**83**) displays excited-state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT) featured two emission bands and performs highly selective and sensitive recognition to Cu^{2+} through two emissions simultaneous quenching. The on-site formed Cu^{2+} complex exhibits excellent selectivity to S^{2-} with fluorescence "off-on" response via Cu^{2+} displacement approach, which exerts ESIPT recovery. Thus, through modulation the ESIPT state of sensor (**83**), relay recognition of Cu^{2+} and S^{2-} in water has been achieved.

A fluorescent probe 6-(2,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-5,6-dihydrobenzoimidazo[1,2-*c*]quinazoline (**84**) was designed and synthesized by Wang's group⁷⁸. Its fluorescence can be quenched upon the addition of Cu^{2+} in aqueous media. The binding constant for Cu^{2+} and (**84**) was determined to be $9.56 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-2}$ in DMSO/ H_2O (1 : 1, v/v). The crystal structure of the Cu^{II} complex, revealed that the Schiff base complex formed in the response system of probe (**84**) to Cu^{2+} via Cu^{2+} -assisted C-N bond breakage of the quinazoline ring in (**84**) to form a Schiff base. Consequently, complex was used as a "turn-on" fluorescence chemosensor for direct detection of CN^- . It showed high selectivity to CN^- over a number of anions in the aqueous media. CN^- replaced the probe in the complex to form $[\text{Cu}(\text{CN})_x]^{2-x}$ and fluorescence recovered. The detection limit of CN^- was $4.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$. The cell images showed that the complex could be used to detect intracellular CN^- .

Benzimidazole-based derivative (**85**) has been designed and synthesized by Nandhakumar and co-author as a fluorescent probe highly selective to Cu^{2+} in HEPES-buffered $\text{CH}_3\text{OH}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 : 1, v/v, pH 7.0) solution⁷⁹. The *in situ* formed Cu complex is further utilized to sense the cyanide ions with high selectivity and fluorescence enhancement performance. In addition, the detection limit of Cu^{II} complex for CN^- was also evaluated following the above mentioned method and was calculated to be $1.86 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, which is greater than the upper limit (1.9 μM) for cyanide in drinking water set by the World Health Organization. This result indicates that Cu complex has a limitation in detection of cyanide in drinking water, but it still has the potential utility to detect cyanide concentration in highly cyanide polluted water. This result indicates that Cu complex has a limitation in detection of cyanide in drinking water. But it still has the potential utility to detect cyanide concentration in highly cyanide polluted water. Tang's group reports another example of sequential recognition of Cu^{2+} and CN^- by a new benzimidazole-containing quinazoline based probe (**86**)⁸⁰.

Probe (**86**) exhibits highly selective and sensitive fluorescence "off-on" recognition properties to Cu^{2+} ion in $\text{EtOH}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1/1, v/v, HEPES 20 mM, pH 7.0) solution with a 2 : 1 binding stoichiometry. The *in situ* prepared Cu^{II} complex solution displays high selectivity to CN^- through fluorescence relay enhancement. This Cu^{2+} and CN^- sequential recognition via fluorescence relay enhancement make probe (**86**) has a potential utility for Cu^{2+} and CN^- detection in aqueous media. In this case the detection limit of Cu^{II} complex for CN^- was also evaluated and was calculated to be $1.74 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$, which is smaller than the upper limit 1.9 μM for cyanide in drinking water defined by the World Health Organization, thus Cu complex probe has a potential utility in detection of cyanide in drinking water as well as cyanide polluted water. Subsequently, the reversibility of the cyanide recognition process was also evaluated. Upon further addition of excess Cu^{2+} to the Cu complex + CN^- solution, the fluorescence spectrum of the resulted solution is almost identical with that of Cu complex solution, which demonstrates that the cyanide recognition process is reversible.

In this field a water soluble non-fluorescent copper(II) complex (**87**)⁸¹ behaves as a highly selective and sensitive for HSO_4^- ions through the enhancement of fluorescence of the system based on intermolecular hydrogen bonding assisted chelation enhanced fluorescence (CHEF) process in "turn-on" style, which has been confirmed by systematic optical techniques and electrochemical studies. This mode of sensing pathway and binding of HSO_4^- ions with the receptor (**87**) has also been validated by optimizing the structures of Cu complex and HSO_4^- adduct with the help of theoretical calculations. This non-cytotoxic probe senses HSO_4^- ions as low as $3.18 \times 10^{-7} \text{ M}$ in water : DMSO (9 : 1, v/v) at biological pH (using 1 mM HEPES buffer) and it is also useful for the detection of intracellular HSO_4^- ions under a fluorescence microscope.

Table 3. Benzimidazole based chemosensors for both cations and anions*For neutral molecules :*

Amongst various reports where compounds behave as sensor for neutral molecules an azo dye-coupled benzimidazole-based receptor (**88**) was synthesized and investigated as a receptor for metal ions in semi-aqueous medium by Singh *et al.*⁸². The receptor recognizes Cu²⁺ with high selectivity over other metal ions. The resultant complex was found to selectively bind oxalic acid via counter ion displacement.

L-Valine derived benzimidazole based bis-urea (**89**)

has been designed and synthesized by Ghosh *et al.* The bis-urea (**89**) (viz. Table 4) is found to act as enantioselective chemosensor for tartrate. The sensor shows greater fluorescence response for L-tartrate in DMSO⁸³. In comparison, less steric receptor (**90**) exhibits a marginal preference for D-tartrate over the L-tartrate in DMSO and validates the steric role of the substituents around the benzimidazole motif in (**89**) toward enantioselective recognition of tartrate.

Wang's group designed and synthesized 1,3,5-

Table 4. Benzimidazole based chemosensors for neutral molecules

tri(1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazol-2-yl)benzene derivatives, as a fluorescent chemosensor (91) (which has structural similarities with compound (57)) for the detection of nitroaromatic explosives, by simple N-hydrocarbylation⁸⁴. Among 16 obtained compounds, compound (91) has the best capability for detection of

picric acid (PA), having good selectivity and high sensitivity. The detection of PA with (91) solution-coated paper strips at the picogram level is developed. A simple, portable, and low cost method is provided for detecting PA in solution and contact mode. Benzimidazole receptors have also been used for the recogni-

tion of neutral receptors as carboxylic acids, hydrogen bond donors, as urea or barbital, and O-methylated aminoacids. Neutral molecules are in general weakly bound and a better control of the complementarity between host and guest is then required.

Moran and co-workers showed a receptor (**92**) for carboxylic acids that connects two benzimidazole units through a xanthene molecule in a tweezer-like structure⁸⁵. The cavity created between the two benzimidazole arms effectively binds methanol, DMSO or acetone in chloroform and the structure of the complexes was determined by single X-ray crystal diffraction. When carboxylic acids were studied, it was observed that the acid group protonates one of the nitrogen atoms present in the benzimidazole moieties while the other remains neutral and participates in the coordination of the resulting anion. When the acid used was anthracene carboxylic acid, a strong decrease of the emission intensity was observed compared to the free acid through a PET mechanism responsible for the quenching of fluorescence. The single crystal structure for the complex shows how the benzimidazole on the amide arm protonates while this NH and the other three NH groups coordinate the carboxylate moiety.

Gale and co-workers prepared a simple tweezer-like receptor (**93**) connecting two benzimidazole units through a 2,6-pyridinedicarboxylic amide⁸⁶. Receptor (**93**) binds preferentially with barbital over the structurally related urea, thiourea or imidazolinone in DMSO/MeNO₂. In the crystal structure of the complex a good complementarity is observed that leads to the formation of four hydrogen bonds.

Other examples of the use of benzimidazole in molecular recognition are the two related macrocycles with the general structure (**94**) in which these heterocycles are connected through polyether alkyl chains⁸⁷. These compounds have been used for the recognition of O-methylated α -aminoacids in chloroform. In the study it has been observed how the length of the macrocyclic arms influences the selectivity due to the complementarity of hydrogen bonds and π - π stacking.

Das *et al.* developed a benzimidazole-derived ICT-based probe, (**95**) for trace level determination of water⁸⁸. In presence of water, the “naked-eye” color of (**95**) changes from red to yellow, while it turns to green from red under UV light. Upon addition of water, (**115**) shows a ratiometric absorbance change in methanol.

Recently a newly designed rhodamine-benzimidazole hybrid molecule (**96**) has been developed⁸⁹ as a FRET-based chemosensor for the selective detection of trace level water in both polar protic and aprotic organic solvents.

Pyrazole based compounds as chemosensor

Pyrazoles are important nitrogen containing 5-membered heterocyclic compounds with stronger fluorescence, have higher hole-transport efficiency and excellent emitting blueness property. Therefore, pyrazoline derivatives have widely been used as whitening or brightening reagents for synthetic fibers, fluorescent chemosensors for recognition of transition metal ions, hole-transport materials in the electrophotography and electroluminescence fields⁹⁰. Moreover, pyrazoline with membrane permeability, low toxicity, and high quantum yield render the fluorophore attractive for biological applications^{91,92}. However, a few pyrazoline derivatives are as effective “turn-on” fluorescent sensors in literature.

Li and co-authors have developed a chromogenic and fluorescent probe (**97**), (Table 5) based on an anion catalyzed intramolecular hydrogen transfer, which displayed drastic changes in UV-Vis absorption as well as fluorescence emission intensities showing selectively for F⁻ over other anions⁹³.

According to Li's group two simple fluorescent anion receptors based on 1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazole-5-one-4-one-phenylhydrazone (**98**) and 1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazole-5-one-4-one *p*-nitrophenyl-hydrazone (**99**) with similar configuration exhibited different anion binding behaviors in DMSO solution⁹⁴. The experimental results indicate that (**98**) bind anions such as F⁻, AcO⁻, H₂PO₄⁻ ions in 2 : 1 host-guest complexation fashion, while (**99**) bind anions in 1 : 1 host-

guest complexation in the solution. Here, the anion binding ability of the receptors both (**98** and **99**) was evaluated through UV-Vis titrations. Upon the addition of fluoride ions in case of (**98**) a significant decrease in the absorption of 394 nm and appearance of two new absorption peaks at 306 nm and 431 nm with two isosbestic points at 346 nm and 410 nm. But, in the case of (**99**), out of two absorption bands at 407 nm and 537 nm, a significant decrease in the absorption band at 407 nm and an increase in the absorption of 537 nm upon addition of F⁻ ions accompanied by a “naked-eye” color changes from red to purple have been recorded. Here, (**98** and **99**) displayed a tautomeric equilibrium between the hydrazone form and the azophenol form. Where the hydrazone form dominated in the solution. Upon addition of the strong basic anions, the hydrazone form would be transferred to the azophenol form, which interacts with anionic analytes and is responsible for the spectral changes and “naked-eye” color changes, established also by the ¹H NMR titration experiment. Upon excitation at 397 nm, (**98**) showed a weak emission at 415 nm and the visible fluorescent enhancement was observed with addition of the strong basic anions such as F⁻. However, (**99**) exhibited a fluorescent emission band centered at 667 nm where the λ_{ex} is 450 nm and such emission would be gradually quenched upon addition of fluoride ions. The possible explanation for this result might be that the receptors (**98** and **99**) employed two different signaling transduction mechanisms for anion binding. Upon complexation with anions, the configuration of (**98**) was rigidified, resulting in inhibiting vibrational and rotational relaxation modes of non-radiative decay, and thus the fluorescent enhancement of (**99**) takes place. In the case of (**99**), introduction of an electron-withdrawing substituent (-NO₂) would be a photoinduced electronic transfer (PET) from the pyrazole unit (a fluorophore) to the electron-withdrawing substituent (-NO₂) and as a result the fluorescent emission would be gradually quenched upon addition of fluoride ions. Merkok *et al.* used N-alkylaminopyrazole ligands (**100** and **101**) in a proof-of-concept fluorescent sensor that can operate as a

simple ‘paper test’ for rapid and highly sensitive mercury detection in water⁹⁵. A significant enhancement of fluorescence emission in aqueous media for the Hg²⁺ detection at concentrations lower than 0.1 ppb is achieved. A linear range from 10 to 100 ppb [Hg²⁺] was obtained in the paper-based system. Two respective contradictory “turn-on” and “turn-off” fluorescence mechanisms in the ‘paper test’ and water solution (pH 1) systems can be explained by the concept of PET, CHEF and H-bonded interaction.

Zhang’s group develop a pyrazoline-based fluorescent sensor (**102**) for biological Zn²⁺ detection⁹⁶. The sensor shows good binding selectivity for Zn²⁺ over competing metal with 40-fold fluorescence enhancement in response to Zn²⁺ presumably due to the blocking of the photoinduced electron transfer (PET) process upon complexation with Zn²⁺. The probe is cell-permeable and can be used to detect intracellular zinc ions in living neuron cells.

The synthesis, characterization, binding and deprotonation studies with anions for four 5-(1*H*-indol-3-yl)-pyrazolyl derivatives (**103-106**) have been described by Ahmad *et al.*⁹⁷. It is worthy to mention that sensor (**103**) shows a drastic change in absorption spectrum (*ca.* 335 nm) and colour (colourless to blue) upon addition of F⁻ in DMSO solution due to the deprotonation of indole -NH proton, as confirmed by ¹H NMR titration. Sensor (**105**) recognizes F⁻ and CN⁻ ions by deprotonation mechanism with visible colour change of the solution in a similar manner to that of (**103**). However, in contrary to (**103** and **105**), sensor (**104**) binds with F⁻, CN⁻, H₂PO₄⁻, AcO⁻ and PhCOO⁻ ions exploiting hydrogen-bonding interaction with the shifting of absorption band to longer wavelength and subsequent colour change of the solution. Compound (**106**) recognizes F⁻ without any visual colour change and its binding is studied by ¹H NMR titration to acquire the important information about the nature of binding between F⁻ and (**106**).

Zhao and co-authors present the preparation of a pyrazoline compound and the properties of its UV-Vis absorption and fluorescence emission⁹⁸. The structure of the compound was characterized by IR, ¹H NMR

and HRMS. Moreover, this compound can be used to determine Hg^{2+} ion with selectivity and sensitivity in the $\text{EtOH} : \text{H}_2\text{O} = 9 : 1$ (v/v) solution. This sensor forms a 1 : 1 complex with Hg^{2+} and shows a fluorescent enhancement with good tolerance of other metal ions. The association constant K_a measured for coordination of the sensor with Hg^{2+} was $3.03 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$, and the detection limit of the sensor toward Hg^{2+} was $3.85 \times 10^{-10} \text{ M}$. Detailed information on the interactions between (107) and Hg^{2+} ion from ^1H NMR spectroscopic studies suggested that the nitrogen atoms in the benzimidazole, thioamide and pyrazoline of the sensor (107) participated to the complex with Hg^{2+} . In addition, the fluorescent probe has practical application in cells imaging.

Wong and co-workers told about a luminescent cyclometalated iridium(III) complex-based chemosensor (108) bearing a zinc-specific receptor, tris(2-pyridylmethyl)amine, and the 3-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazole ligand showed a pronounced luminescence color change from blue to green upon addition of Zn^{2+} ions to a solution of iridium(III) complex⁹⁹. It is attributed to the suppression of photoinduced electron transfer upon complexation of iridium(III) complex with Zn^{2+} ions, which interaction has been established by UV-Vis absorption titration, emission titration, and ^1H NMR titration. Selectivity of this iridium(III) complex (108) for Zn^{2+} over other common metal ions and the application of this probe in visualizing intracellular Zn^{2+} distribution in live zebrafish have been demonstrated.

Table 5. Pyrazole based chemosensors recognising ions

(108)

(109)

R= H (110)

R=CH₃ (111)

(112)

(113)

(114)

(115)

The design, synthesis, and photophysical properties of a new fluorene-based fluorescent chemosensor, 4-((*E*)-2-(2-(benzo[*d*]thiazol-2-yl)-9,9-diethyl-9*H*-fluoren-7-yl)vinyl)-*N,N*-bis((3,5-dimethyl-1*H*-pyrazol-1-yl)methyl)benzenamine (**109**), is described by Frazer and co-workers for the detection of Al³⁺¹⁰⁰. Fluorescent probe (**109**) exhibited absorption at 382 nm and strong fluorescence emission at 542 nm (fluorescence quantum yield, Φ_F , of 0.80). The capture of Al³⁺ by the pyrazolyl aniline receptor resulted in nominal change

in the linear absorption (372 nm) but a large hypsochromic shift of 161 nm in the fluorescence spectrum (542 to 433 nm, $\Phi_F=0.88$), from which Al³⁺ was detected both ratiometrically and colorimetrically. The large hypsochromic shift could be attributed to a reduction in intermolecular charge transfer (ICT). This dramatic result found with Al³⁺ and the probe may be a consequence of the size and polarizability of the Al³⁺ ion. The Al³⁺ is believed to interact strongly with the pyrazolyl nitrogens and, even though the resulting

molecular assemblies are unknown, it is believed to restrict the excited state vibrations of the chromophore, resulting in an increase in fluorescence properties. A single set of isobestic points was observed in both the absorption and emission spectra, suggesting a single equilibrium was reached in complexation. The addition of other metal ions, namely Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} and Pb^{2+} produced only minimal changes in the optical properties of this probe. The emission band of this probe was also accessed by two-photon excitation in the near-IR, as two-photon absorption (2PA) is important for potential applications in two-photon fluorescence microscopy (2PFM) imaging. The 2PA cross section of the free fluorenyl ligand (**109**) was 220 GM at 810 nm and 235 GM at 810 nm for the Al-ligand complex, practically useful properties for 2PFM. The probe exhibited a peak absorption at 382 nm and a gradually blue-shift upon the sequential addition of Al^{3+} . The emission spectra of the free ligand titrated with Al^{3+} resulted in the appearance of a new fluorescence band at 432 nm, shifted from 532 nm for the pure ligand.

Two novel rhodamine-pyrazolone-based colorimetric “off-on” fluorescent chemosensors for Fe^{3+} ions were designed and synthesized by Jadeja *et al.* using pyrazolone as the recognition moiety and rhodamine 6G as the signalling moiety¹⁰¹. The photophysical properties and Fe^{3+} -binding properties of sensors (**110**) and (**111**) in acetonitrile-aqueous solution were also investigated. Both sensors successfully exhibit a remarkably “turn-on” response, toward Fe^{3+} , which was attributed to 1 : 2 complex formation between Fe^{3+} and the two receptors. After the addition of metal ions, UV/Vis absorption spectra showed a distinct change and the appearance of a new spectral band with a maximum at 530 nm for Fe^{3+} ions. The absorption band at 530 nm in the case of Fe^{3+} is due to the formation of a delocalized xanthane moiety of rhodamine by selective Fe^{3+} -induced ring opening of spirolactam, which also explains the change in colour from colourless to pink in the presence of this Fe^{3+} ion. Without metal ions, probe (**110**) and (**111**) show almost no fluorescence upon excitation at 530 nm, suggesting that receptors (**110**) and (**111**) exist in a ring-closed non-

fluorescent spirolactam conformation.

Das *et al.* synthesized a new chemosensor (**112**) and its spectral response was screened with most alkali, alkaline earth, transition and lanthanide metal ions in THF-water (2 : 3, v/v, pH 7.2, 20 mM HEPES buffer) medium¹⁰². This is found to bind four different transition metal ions such as Hg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ag^{+} and Ni^{2+} in mixed aqueous solution at pH 7.2; while binding affinity towards the Hg^{2+} is found to be an order of magnitude higher as compared to other three cations mentioned. The fluorescence quenching of these metal ions could be explained based on the spin-orbit coupling phenomena. Observed luminescence change for Hg^{2+} was more appreciable than the other three metal ions for a comparable concentration of the respective metal ion. Chemosensor (**112**) has an anthracenyl unit as the signalling moiety, covalently coupled to an N-N donor receptor fragment. Fluorescence based emission read-out signal of the anthracenyl unit is governed by different photoinduced electron transfer (PET) processes in the absence and presence of the coordinated metal ion. Experimental studies revealed that pyridyl pyrazole, used as the receptor fragment for Hg^{2+} showed a higher affinity for this ion in aqueous/organic media. Experimental results reveal that the (**112**) could be used for colorimetric detection of Hg^{2+} , present in the lower organism like *Pseudomonas putida*.

Yang's group reported a new pyrazole-based fluorescent sensor, 5-amino-3-(5-phenyl-1H-pyrrol-2-yl)-1H-pyrazole-4-carboxamide (**113**), and studied for fluoride anion (F^{-}) detection in organic or water-containing solution¹⁰³. This compound displayed both changes in UV-Vis absorption and fluorescence emission spectra upon addition of F^{-} . With increasing of F^{-} , blue emission intensity increases drastically and reaches saturation with 607-fold enhancement at 424 nm. The results indicate that (**113**) has highly selectivity for fluoride detection over other anions, such as Cl^{-} , Br^{-} , I^{-} , HSO_4^{-} , $\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4^{-}$ and AcO^{-} in DMSO or aqueous DMSO solutions. ¹H NMR titration and other experiments confirm that the sensing process is mainly from

the deprotonation of the pyrazole-NH in (113). Because of the high charge density and small size, fluoride as strong base can deprotonate the compound (113) to afford deeply the heterocyclic conjugated anion which gives strong emission when excited at 365 nm.

Qin's group reported an original Schiff base type fluorescent chemosensor 1-phenyl-3-methyl-5-hydroxypyrazole-4-carbaldehyde(benzoyl)hydrazone (114) for Cu^{2+} ¹⁰⁴. An obvious fluorescence quenching only for Cu^{2+} demonstrates that ligand (114) exhibits high selectivity and efficient signaling behavior toward micromolar concentration of Cu^{2+} compared with other metal ions. At the same time, the coordination form between ligand and Cu^{2+} is elucidated via crystal structure. The paramagnetic nature of Cu^{2+} and the Cu^{2+} -F interaction was the cause of fluorescence quenching.

A structurally characterized naphthelene-pyrazol conjugate (115) behaves as an Al^{III} ion-selective chemosensor through internal charge transfer (ICT)-chelation-enhanced fluorescence (CHEF) processes in 100 mM HEPES buffer (water-DMSO 5 : 1, v/v) at biological pH with almost no interference of other competitive ions¹⁰⁵. The probe can detect Al^{3+} ions as low as 31.78 nM within a very short response time (15–20 s).

Conclusions

The important progress achieved in the development of diazole based receptors can be exemplified by the number of systems that have recently been described in this field. In most cases, such receptors are able to recognize either cations or anions. Although too many diazole derivatives have been devised as probes for the detection of several types of cationic/anionic/neutral species with help of different photophysical processes, comparatively more imidazole/benzimidazole based compounds including their metal chelates have showed imperative photophysical properties in favour of developing the fluorescent chemosensors highly selective for the target species. Among the explored chemosensors for cations, several Zn^{2+} sensors have been reported. Here, the ben-

zimidazole based compound, 2,6-bis(5,6-dihydrobenzo[4,5]imidazo[1,2-c]quinazolin-6-yl)-4-methylphenol³⁶ is the most superior one as it is highly sensitive and can detect Zn^{2+} ions as low as 0.53 nM in almost aqueous medium at biological pH, and this probe is also efficient to detect the distribution of Zn^{2+} ions in living cells like other diazole- Zn^{2+} sensors¹⁰⁶. Interestingly it is noteworthy to mention that the diazole derivative is capable to detect Al^{3+} ions as low as 9.0 nM in green solvent system comparable with the lowest LOD available in the literature¹⁰⁷. In case of anion detection, this derivatives are not good enough compared to the detection cations in terms of LOD, solvent systems. The diazole derivatives are also important to detect the neutral molecules like picric acid, tartarate, etc.; some toxic anions and also cations of different oxidation states. And, this review indicates that more imidazole/benzimidazole based compounds have been explored in developing the chemosensors for different species compared to the pyrazole based chemosensors. As a consequence of this background, we thus predict that this topic constitutes an area of supramolecular chemistry that is ripe for future growth.

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